

Evaluating Virtual Reality Applications based on Dominant Hand

Mochammad Hannats Hanafi Ichsan^{1,4}, Cecilia Sik-Lanyi^{1,2}, Tibor Guzsvinecz³

¹ Department of Electrical Engineering and Information Systems, Faculty of Information Technology, University of Pannonia, Egyetem u. 10, 8200 Veszprem, Hungary

² Hungarian Research Network, Piarista u. 4. 1052 Budapest, Hungary

³ Department of Information Technology and its Applications, Faculty of Information Technology, University of Pannonia, Gasparich M. utca 18/A, 8900 Zalaegerszeg, Hungary

⁴ Department of Informatics, Faculty of Computer Science, Brawijaya University, Malang, Indonesia

¹hanas.hanafi@phd.mik.uni-pannon.hu, ²lanyi.cecilia@mik.uni-pannon.hu, ³guzsvinecz.tibor@zek.uni-pannon.hu

Abstract: Virtual reality (VR) has evolved as a strong technology which is capable of providing people with immersive and engaging experiences. This study investigates the view of left-handed people on the importance of adaptable VR development. It demonstrates that left-handedness may include specific cognitive talents useful in VR environments. However, present VR technologies offer difficulties for left-handed users because they are primarily built for right-handed people. This review supports the creation of customizable VR environments for both left- and right-handed users, to improve accessibility and usability through the utilization of essential VR aspects (Virtual Environment, Immersion, Feedback, Interactivity, and Participant). This study emphasizes the significance of more research in developing inclusive VR solutions for left-handed users.

Introduction

Virtual reality (VR) has evolved into a potent technology capable of offering immersive and engaging experiences, and providing several great developments for a variety of industries such as education, rehabilitation, and entertainment [1], among others. Slater and Sánchez-Vives [2] introduced the notion of "presence" in virtual reality applications, stressing the subjective sensation of being in a virtual world. They also clarified that VR offers inclusive experiences for both left-handed and right-handed users, that help

to make real-world activities and can help to be accessible to persons with physical or cultural constraints. Gerling and Spiel [3] investigated the revolutionary potential of virtual reality in solving accessibility issues. They explain how VR technology might be developed to deliver inclusive experiences, allowing a greater spectrum of people to participate in activities and surroundings.

Additionally, the discussion about the growth of VR users has been observed in previous research [4]. They emphasized that currently, it becomes significant to design accessible and usable VR applications to benefit both left-handed and right-handed people in some areas (i.e., health, entertainment, and education studies).

However, the ratio of investigations that focus on developing VR applications that consider inclusiveness, especially for people with various dominant hands is fairly limited. Therefore, first of all, there is a lack of research to provide the theoretical framework or human factor guidelines that could support designers when developing accessible VR applications. Secondly, very limited work has addressed VR design for specific issues regarding dominant hands.

To respond to these two addressed research gaps, this paper first demonstrates some key elements of virtual reality as the foundation/direction of future development [5]. Additionally, this study provides our findings and recommendations for further work to tackle our addressed research gaps.

Materials and Methods

A literature review was conducted to demonstrate our research approach to get the best answers to our following research question.

RQ: Does the VR system development process require the perspective of left-handed people?

The technique for conducting the literature review includes keyword selection, searching for all noteworthy articles using predetermined criteria, filtering, categorization, identify RQs, evaluate the quality of the publications, and summarize and interpret the findings. The Web of Science was chosen as the search engine/database, while "Virtual Reality" and "Handedness" were the chosen keywords. The search period set from 2021 to 2023. Then we conducted our systematic review to locating and assessing literature.

After filtering, 23 records were finalized to evaluate that information is relevant to our study aims. Four publications were excluded because they did

not discuss the development for people with various dominant hands. Also, 12 papers were removed because they did not establish a left-handed viewpoint application. Finally, we found seven studies that used left-handed and right-handed design considerations to create VR applications and satisfied all of our requirements for this literature study. Among these seven selected studies, three of them specified how many individuals were left-handed and right-handed during their testing, whereas the other four did not disclose the number of participants and just designed the program to accommodate any people with different dominant hands.

Discussion

In order to narrow down the potential of the VR system development process that requires the perspective of left-handed persons, this section discusses studied related literature covering VR applications and handedness concerns.

According to our review, we can identify five key elements of VR including virtual environment, immersion, feedback, interactivity, and participant which have been explained in detail as follows:

1. Virtual Environment:

The virtual environment is a computer-generated space where users interact via avatars in 2D, 3D or other graphical representations[6, 7].

2. Immersion:

From a psychological standpoint, immersion is the condition of total participation in an action while it is being performed. It is a state in which a participant becomes so involved and invested in a virtual world that their mind becomes disconnected from the real location in which they are actually present. There are two kinds of immersion: mental [8] and physical [6]. Watching a movie, listening to music, and daydreaming are all examples of mental absorption. When we get physically absorbed in an activity or event, we experience physical immersion.

3. Feedback:

Feedback allows participants to see the results of their inputs. A virtual display, for example, should refresh its image when a person moves their head [7, 9]. To be more specific, the display in a virtual world should depict what is on the participant's corresponding side.

4. Interactivity:

Interactivity is essential in a virtual reality experience because it allows players to interact with and modify the virtual world. Sensors and other devices are utilized to assist interaction, allowing participants to engage with virtual objects in real time via navigation, direct manipulation, or other methods [10, 11].

5. Participants:

Virtual reality experiences rely significantly on human engagement. Participants come from a variety of backgrounds and have varied degrees of expertise. As a result, it is critical to research and respond to their demands.

According to Table 1, all of the research develops virtual environment for users' virtual space. Mitre-Ortiz et. al. [6] used game narratives to enhance motivation and immersion aspects. While Fiset and Lamontagne [8] used immersion to make people feel as if they are in a room. In this study, they obtained favorable findings in terms of immersion level.

Table 1. Summary of VR Design for left-handed and right-handed people.

No	The use of key elements of virtual reality	Reference	VR application
1	1, 2, 5	[6]	Model Development with Hand Motion
2	1, 3, 4, 5	[10]	Functional Lateralization in Healthy Adults
3	1, 3, 5	[7]	Hand Dominance of Virtual Reach Control
4	1, 3, 5	[9]	Virtual Reality-Based Mirror Visual Feedback System
5	1, 3, 4, 5	[11]	Human-Robot Haptic Interaction
6	1, 2, 3, 5	[8]	Visuo-Locomotor in Virtual Pedestrian
7	1, 3, 5	[12]	Motor Learning in Stroke Survivor

Besides, feedback is a critical component in the amount of engagement between VR and humans. The first type of feedback is input/output data presented on the screen [6], such as mirror reflection [9], audio/sound [10], and haptic [11]. Feedback on the screen can take the form of success in holding a ball [7], a cube [9] or body motions in a virtual environment [8].

Additionally, the head mounted display (HMD) is the main device used to view into the virtual world, such as Oculus Rift [7], Meta Quest [9], and HTC Vive Pro Eye [8] as well as additional controllers using Velcro glove marker-clusters [7] and Impedance Controller [11]. Last but not least, three research

included both left-handed and right-handed people [6, 9, 11]. The remaining four research do not include participants, but they are in the concept and design stages for anybody with any handedness [7, 8, 10, 12].

It is critical to include the views of both right and left-handed people during the iterative and user-centric process of building VR systems. Recognizing hand dominance variety means that VR interfaces are tailored to fit users' natural tendencies and preferences. By using an inclusive design approach, VR systems may improve user satisfaction, ease of use, and usability for a larger range of people.

The review's limitations are that certain prominent academic journal publishers may not be included, and some papers have also been excluded. We excluded these studies because they did not mention or had no participants who were left-handed. This searching constraint contributes to a shortage of selected papers. In the future, our research will broaden the variety of searchable publications.

Conclusions

This paper intends to identify virtual reality studies for the people with various dominant hands and summarize their strength with five components of virtual reality: virtual environment, immersion, feedback, interactivity, and participants. The finding of this study is an approach that must be taken when developing a VR application for any handedness.

To conclude, we can state that: VR system development process require the perspective of right and left-handed people. The domain analysis was proved in terms of both right and left-handedness in a review of seven articles. It provides insight into the present state of handedness in VR application development and also indicates to my future determination of a specific VR area.

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